

TA'LIMDA EHTIYOJI BO'LGAN IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN BOLALAR VA O'SMIRLARNING TA'LIM OLISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ta'lim muassasasida ta'limda alohida ehtiyoji bo'lgan imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va o'smirlarning ta'lim olishlari uchun zarur psixologo – pedagogik, korreksion sharoitlar yaratish, ularning imkoniyatiga yo'naltirilgan umumta'lim dasturlari va korreksion ishlarni amalga oshirish orqali ruhiy rivojlanishini, ijtimoiy moslashtirishni amalga oshirish;

Kalit so'zlar: tiflopedagogika, surdopedagogika, tiflopedagogika, oligofrenopedagogika.

EDUCATION OF CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH EDUCATIONAL NEEDS

Abstract. Creating the necessary psychological-pedagogical and correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with special educational needs in an educational institution, as well as their mental development by implementing general education programs and correctional work aimed at their ability, implementation of social adjustment;

Key words: typhlopedagogy, deaf pedagogy, typhlopedagogy, oligophrenopedagogy.

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ С ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫМИ ПОТРЕБНОСТЯМИ

Аннотация. Путем создания необходимых психолого-педагогических и коррекционных условий для обучения детей и подростков с особыми потребностями в обучении в образовательном учреждении, путем реализации общеобразовательных программ и коррекционной работы, ориентированной на их способности, осуществления психического развития, социальной адаптации;

Ключевые слова: тифлопедагогика, сурдопедагогика, тифлопедагогика, олигофренопедагогика.

Alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalar toifalari, ularni o'qitish, tarbiyalash, ijtimoiy- mehnatga moslashuvi masalalari bilan tanishtiradi. Bu bilimlar kelajakdagi pedagoglarga o'quvchilardagi o'zlashtirmovchilikning sababalarini erta aniqlash va ota-onalarga ta'lim muassasalarini to'g'ri tanlashga yordam beradi.

Bola rivojlanishidagi nuqsonlar har xil bo'ladi, ularning ba'zilar batamom bartaraf etiladi, ba'zilar bir qadar tuzatiladi, korreksiyalanadi, bilinmaydigan holga keltiriladi, boshqalari esa kompensatsiyalanadi. Masalan, bola nutqida og'ir nuqson bo'lsa, ilk yoshda to'g'ri tashkil etilgan logopedik chora-tadbirlar ta'sirida uni to'liq bartaraf etish mumkin. Boladagi nuqson markaziy nerv sistemasidagi organik kamchiliklar natijasida paydo bo'lgan bo'lsa (masalan, aqli zaiflik shunday nuqson jumlasiga kiradi), uni to'liq bartaraf etib bo'lmasa ham, biroq kamaytirish, ko'zga ko'rinmaydigan, sezilmaydigan darajagacha tuzatish mumkin. Maxsus pedagogika amaliyotida yana shunday toifadagi alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalar kuzatiladiki, nuqsonni tuzatib ham, korreksiyalab ham bo'lmaydi, masalan, tug'ma ko'rlik yoki karlikning ayrim turlari shular jumlasidandir. Bunda ko'rish analizatorining vazifasini sezgi organlariga, eshitish analizatorining vazifasini esa ko'rish analizatoriga yuklash, ya'ni kompensatsiyalash, o'rnini bosish mumkin. Ko'rish qobiliyati zaif bolalar sezgi organlariga tayangan holda barmoqlari bilan Brayl shriftidan foydalanadilar. Bunda harf olti nuqta kombinatsiyasi bilan belgilanadi. Eshitish qobiliyatida

muammosi bo'lgan bolalar esa imoishora, daktil nutqdan, barmoqlar harakati bilan anglatiladigan nutqdan foydalanishlari mumkin. Korreksion pedagogika fanining rivojlanishi natijasida undan quyidagi tarmoqlari mustaqil fan sifatida ajralib chiqdi:

- surdopedagogika (lotincha surdus – kar, gung so'zidan olingan) eshitishida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarning ta'lim tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanadigan fan;
- tiflopedagogika (yunoncha tiflos – ko'r, so'qir so'zidan olingan) – ko'zi ojiz bolalarning ta'lim-tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanadigan fan;
- oligofrenopedagogika (yunoncha oligos – kam, fren – aql), so'zlaridan olingan, – aqliy tomondan zaif bolalarning ta'lim-tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanadigan fan;
- logopediya (yunoncha logos – so'z, padeo – tarbiya so'zlaridan olingan) – og'ir nuq nuqsonlarini o'rganish, oldini olish, bartaraf etish yo'llari, usullarini o'rganadigan fan. Respublikamizning barcha viloyatlarida zamon talablariga muvofiq alohida yordamga muhtoj bolalarning differensial va integratsiyalashgan, inklyuziv ta'limi barcha yo'nalishlar bo'yicha jadal sura'tlar bilan rivojlanmoqda.

Inklyuziv ta'lim vazifalari:

- Ta'lim muassasasida ta'limda alohida ehtiyoji bo'lgan imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va o'smirlarning ta'lim olishlari uchun zarur psixologo – pedagogik, korreksion sharoitlar yaratish, ularning imkoniyatiga yo'naltirilgan umumta'lim dasturlari va korreksion ishlarni amalga oshirish orqali ruhiy rivojlanishini, ijtimoiy moslashtirishni amalga oshirish;
- Maxsus ta'lim muassasasi o'quvchilarini umumta'lim maktablari bilan uyg'unlashtirgan holda faoliyat olib borish yo'li bilan o'quvchilarning ta'limdagi tenglik huquqini kafolatlash;
- Jamiyatning va oilaning faol ishtirokida nogiron va sog'lom bolalar o'rtasidagi to'siqlarni bartaraf etish, bolaning ehtiyojlarini qondirish, ijtimoiy hayotga erta moslashtirish; 8 Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va o'smirlarni oilalardan ajralmagan holda yashash huquqini ro'yobga chiqarish;
- Jamiyatda imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar va o'smirlarga muqobil munosabatni shakllantirishdir.

“Integratsiya” tushunchasi ingliz tilidan olingan bo'lib, integrative – qo'shiluvchi, birlashuvchi, integration – qo'shilish, birlashish degan manoni bildiradi. Volferen Bergerning yozishicha: “Integratsion ta'lim bu – segregason ta'limning aksi bo'lib, bunda maxsus ehtiyojga ega bolalar umumta'lim muassasalari tizimiga kiritiladi”.

Integratsiya keng, ma'noda ijtimoiy integratsiya yoki jamiyatga integratsiya va pedagogik integratsiya yoki ta'limga integratsiyani o'z ichiga oladi.

Ijtimoiy integratsiya – rivojlanishida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolani ijtimoiy munosabatlar va xatti-harakatlarning umumiy tizimiga ijtimoiy adaptatsiyasidir. Nogiron bolani jamiyatga integratsiyasi muammosi bir tomondan, psixik va jismoniy rivojlanish kamchiliklarini mavjudligi bilan, ikkinchi tomondan ijtimoiy munosabatlar tizimini mukammal emasligi, ya'ni ba'zi talablarini ma'lum darajada keskinligi hayot faoliyati cheklangan bola uchun o'ta olmaydigan to'siqqa aylanishi bilan ifodalanadi. Nogironlarni jamiyatga integratsiyasining ikki yondashuvi mavjud. Birinchi yondashuv nogironni jamiyatga integratsiyasini mavjud atrof-muhit shart-sharoitlarga moslashishini nazarda tutadi. Albatta, mazkur yondashuv bir tomonlama va juda tordir. Ikkinchi yondashuv nogironni jamiyatga kirishga tayyorlash va jamiyatni nogiron bolani qabul qilishga tayyorlashni nazarda tutadi. Nogironni jamiyatga kirishga tayyorlash bo'yicha ko'pgina 9 ishlar

amalgama oshirilgan bo'lsada, jamiyatni nogiron bolani qabul qilishga tayyorlash bo'yicha ishlar endi muhokama qilinmoqda.

Jismoniy integratsiya – bolalarni bir binoda faoliyat ko'rsatishi. Muallifning ta'kidlashicha, integratsiyaning bu turi bolalar dunyolari orasidagi masofani qisqartirishning boshlang'ich davridir. Funktsional va ijtimoiy integratsiya uchun predmet-fazoviy birlashuv xosdir. U predmetli munosabatlar, shaxslararo aloqalar, muloqotni tashkil etish orqali amalga oshiriladi.

Ijtimoiy-etali integratsiya ijtimoiy masofalarni to'liq qisqarib ketishi, faoliyatdagi tengququqli hamkorlik, subyekt-subyekt munosabatlarini nazarda tutadi.

Ijtimoiy adaptatsiya – o'zgaruvchan hayot sharoitlariga insonni moslashish qobiliyati bo'lib, u ijtimoiylashuv va integratsiyaning muhim mexanizmidir. Ijtimoiy adaptatsiya turli faoliyatlar (o'yin, muloqot, o'qish, mehnat) va insonni o'zini anglash jarayonida amalga oshadi. Mazkur faoliyat turlari bir vaqtning o'zida hayotning turli bosqichlarida adaptatsiya vositalari, maqsadlari va natijalari sifatida xizmat qiladi.

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